

TABLE 1—R_r VALUE × 100 OF IONS IN TERNARY SYSTEMS

Solvent system	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Bi ³⁺
DMSO : n-butanol : HNO ₃ (50%)					
10 : 84 : 6	24	18	24	83	68
20 : 74 : 6	47	46	47	50	68
DMSO : Isopropanol : HNO ₃ (50%)					
10 : 80 : 10	43	31	39	45	69
20 : 70 : 10	65	62	78	65	91
DMSO : Methyl ethyl ketone : HNO ₃ (50%)					
10 : 80 : 10	54	39	43	58	85
20 : 70 : 10	62	63	63	69	94
30 : 60 : 10	79	83	72	86	96
DMSO : Ethyl acetate : HNO ₃ (50%)					
10 : 80 : 10	41	22	23	30	72

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF BINARY AND TERNARY IONS

Solvent system	Ions separated
DMSO : Isopropanol : HNO ₃ (50%) 20 : 70 : 10	Ni ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ Co ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ Bi ³⁺ -Cd ²⁺ Bi ³⁺ -Cu ²⁺ Cd ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ -Co ²⁺ Cd ²⁺ -Ni ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ Bi ³⁺ -Cd ²⁺ -Co ²⁺ Ni ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺
DMSO : n-butanol : HNO ₃ (50%) 10 : 84 : 6 20 : 74 : 6	Co ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ Co ²⁺ -Cu ²⁺ (d) Ni ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ Ni ²⁺ Cu ²⁺ (d) Co ²⁺ -Cu ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ (d)
DMSO : Methyl ethyl ketone : HNO ₃ (50%) 30 : 60 : 10	Co ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ -Cd ²⁺ Ni ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ Cu ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ -Ni ²⁺ Co ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺

(d)=diffused

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Further Studies in Multiple Boundary Formation During Electrolysis in a W-tube

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As early as 1972 Palit^{1,2} made the intriguing observation that on electrolysis of any dilute electrolyte in a W-tube, sharp stationary boundaries form in the inner tubes generally dividing the solution into three zones—acid, neutral and alkaline. The intermediate neutral zone is not only neutral but is practically depleted of all electrolytes, a behaviour which is just opposite to the prediction of the time honoured Hittorf theory and so can be termed an anti-Hittorf phenomenon. Time taken for such boundary formation, multiplicity and sharpness of

the boundaries, if and whenever formed any, depend on the current density, concentration of the electrolyte³, cell geometry, nature of the solvent⁴ and nature of the electrolyte^{4,5}. Sengupta and Palit⁶ also noted the acceleration of boundary formation by exogenous addition of acids, alkalis as well as salts into the original electrolytic solution and put forward a tentative theory to explain this phenomenon. During electrolysis of a potassium dichromate solution under various conditions the present author observed some interesting features in addition to those reported earlier¹⁻⁶ related to the boundary formation phenomenon, and these are enumerated in the present note.

Band formation in outermost limbs : If initially the lower portion of the W-tube be filled with a mixture of potassium dichromate and a concentrated additional electrolyte (e.g. sodium sulphate), the rest with dichromate solution alone, and the system is electrolysed, a colourless band at the anode limb and a deep coloured band at the cathode limb appear. But the development of such a coloured or colourless thin band does not take place, if the entire solution is initially a mixture of potassium dichromate and sodium sulphate.

Double boundary formation in the outermost tube by adding sugar : When the lower part of the W-tube is filled up with a mixture of K₂Cr₂O₇ (0.01 M) and a concentrated sugar solution, and the rest with original dichromate solution (0.01 M), a spectacular boundary formation takes place at the outermost tubes of the W-tube. Initially a colourless band forms in the lower portion of the outermost limb on the cathode side, which gradually spreads out towards the lower portion of the outermost limb on the anode side, current density simultaneously decreasing from 5 to 0.2 mA. The solution above this band assumes light yellow colour on the cathode side and deep brown colour on the anode side. Another important feature of such electrolysis is that no gas formation takes place at all at the intermediate portion of the tube even after prolonged electrolysis.

Effect of adding solid potassium dichromate after double boundary formation with its solution : If about 0.1 g of K₂Cr₂O₇ is added from the cathode

side just after the double boundary formation in the electrolysis of (0.005 M) $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution in a 16 mm o.d. W-tube, the current density gradually increases from a very low value of 0.2 to about 2.5-3 mA and remains steady at that point thereafter. Besides, the alkaline dichromate colour at the cathode side gradually diminishes and becomes completely colourless after about one week. On the otherhand, the colour of the anode limb becomes darker. Therefore, we come across a situation in which the double boundary formation which is very much common with a W-tube, can be converted to a single boundary just by adding excess electrolyte. Similar phenomenon takes place even with the addition of solid $K_2Cr_2O_7$ from both cathode and anode sides at the same time.

Effect of temperature : Temperature has a pronounced effect on the boundary formation in a W-tube. At higher temperature ($\sim 45^\circ$), the electrolysis of 0.005 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution in a W-tube of 16 mm o.d. and at 20 mA current density gives single boundary at the anode bend. After about 48 h current decreases to 10 mA. On cooling down the electrolytic cell to room temperature double boundary forms and the current density decreases to 0.5 mA. At this stage if the temperature is again increased to 45° , the boundary does not diffuse. With wider tube (32 mm o.d.) whose middle part is of the same height as the cathode and the anode limb, electrolysis of 0.01 M chromic acid at 45° in a thermostat and 15 mA current density does not show any boundary formation for overnight and a few cm³ of gas usually termed as IZ-gas, at the middle portion of the tube is formed. Similar phenomenon is observed with 0.005 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution at 45° . Electrolysis of 0.005 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution in such tube at room temperature takes about 48 h for double boundary formation. Temperature is then increased to 45° , when the boundary diffused and current increased to 12 mA and remained steady thereafter.

Lilliput electrodes—its effect : On electrolysis with lilliput electrodes as cathode and anode, a colourless band first appears at the cathode bend and another boundary appears at the anode bend so that the colour inside the tube from anode to cathode side becomes orange-yellow - colourless band-light yellow. Although, current decreases to 5 mA, the colourless band remains as it is. With the cathode of lilliput size and the foil type anode, the boundary forms quickly. After double boundary formation the colourless band disappears and intermediate zone becomes totally colourless. When the case is reversed by taking lilliput electrode as anode and foil electrode as cathode, little longer time is required for double boundary formation, colourless band remaining at the cathode bend.

Other set-ups equivalent to W-tube : 0.0025 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ is electrolysed in the set up comprising of two 250 ml beakers connected by an inverted U-tube of 10 mm o.d. platinum foil electrodes are introduced separately into the beakers. Current

is passed directly from D.C. mains and within 4 h it becomes 26 mA. No sharp boundary is formed but the solution in the beaker containing the anode becomes darker in colour and that in the other one becomes light yellow. Colour inside the connecting tube becomes deep yellow but on continued electrolysis for overnight, current decreases to 0.8 mA and the middle part becomes colourless. Then another beaker is introduced at the middle to the preceding set-up and connected as before by another inverted U-tube of 10 mm o.d. Here electrolysis of 0.0025 M $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution for overnight makes only one connecting tube nearer the cathode colourless. The solution in the beaker containing cathode becomes light yellow while two other beakers are orange in colour and the second connecting tube is yellow in colour. This situation remains as it is even on further electrolysis.

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Electrochemical Oxidation of Alcohol Held in the Cathode Chamber to Acetic Acid Through Non-Faradaic Electrolysis

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It has been earlier postulated¹ that co-liberation (*i.e.* liberation of a mixture of hydrogen and oxygen) at the cathode during non-Faradaic electrolysis is caused by the formation of $(H_2O)_x^+$ at the anode due to high dielectric constant of water. This H_2O^+ is a free radical ion of oxidative character and so is expected to oxidise substances present in its path of migration to the cathode. Indeed this has been found² to be true, even very stable compounds like chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, *etc* being oxidised when placed in the intermediate zone in the path of the current. If our idea be correct, H_2O^+ formed at the anode would travel towards the cathode and may oxidise substances present at the cathode chamber, though in normal electrolysis the cathode chamber is a seat of reducing activity. Thus under such conditions we may expect to observe the abnormal phenomenon of oxidation in the cathode